

Promoting ocean and water literacy in school communities

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Deliverable D6.3 – Summary of communication actions

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List of Abbreviations

CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
M	Month
OCT	Ocean Conservation Trust
PEDCR	Plan for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results
PML	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
UGC	User-Generated Content
WP	Work Package

Summary

This report provides an overview of the communication activities implemented throughout the ProBleu project under Task 6.3 (Communication materials: visual identity and social media). This document summarises how communication actions were designed, deployed, and managed during the project.

The main objective of this report is to summarise the communication actions, including the development of the visual identity of the project, the deployment of digital communication channels, and the production of communication and outreach materials aimed at increasing the visibility, accessibility, and understanding of ProBleu activities and results among key target audiences, particularly schools and education-related stakeholders.

The communication actions presented in this document include: the creation and use of a coherent visual identity and branded materials, the operation of the project website as a central communication hub, the implementation of social media activities across multiple platforms, the dissemination of newsletters and direct outreach campaigns, media and press-related actions, and the deployment of localised communication initiatives through language ambassadors. These actions were implemented in close coordination with project partners and aligned with the broader dissemination and exploitation objectives of WP6.

This report provides a descriptive account of the communication actions carried out, highlighting their evolution over time and the adjustments made in response to project needs and feedback received during implementation.

1. Introduction

This report documents the communication activities implemented within the ProBleu project under **Task 6.3 (Communication materials: visual identity and social media)**.

Communication actions within ProBleu were coordinated through regular meetings with project partners, ensuring alignment between the overall communication strategy and the practical needs arising during project implementation.

During the initial phase of the project, communication efforts focused primarily on project setup and promotion, including developing the visual identity, core communication materials, and launching the main digital channels. As the project progressed, the communication approach evolved to create materials for the call-for-grants promotion and more targeted materials, particularly to enable ProBleu schools to communicate more effectively about their projects, their participation in the programme, and their contribution to the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”. This shift responded to the growing need for guidance, visibility tools, and ready-to-use resources for schools.

The development of communication materials was carried out collaboratively. For example, **Earthwatch** contributed to the preparation of web content by drafting individual project stories for funded schools; **CSIC** provided close, often individualised follow-up and communication support to participating teachers; **PML** and **KTU** engaged directly with

schools through one-to-one exchanges and collective sessions to address questions related to the project catalogue of teaching aids (<https://probleu.pml.space>) and learning assessment surveys, respectively; **OCT** engaged with a larger network of stakeholders related to ocean and water literacy, and **INOVA+** maintained a dedicated and continuous communication channel for formal and administrative matters.

Collaborative tools, such as Google Drive documents, surveys, Padlets, and Canva templates, were used to collect and monitor communication actions implemented by all partners throughout the project. These tools facilitated the aggregation of inputs across partners and supported internal coordination.

This report complements other project outputs, such as **Deliverable D6.1 (Plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results)**, which defines the strategic framework and planned objectives, and other progress monitoring official periodic reports.

2. Overview of communication actions implemented

This section provides an overview of the communication actions implemented through relevant channels aligned with target audiences and key messages identified in the ProBleu communication framework.

2.1 Visual identity and communication materials

A visual identity was developed at the beginning of the project, and thereafter consistently updated and applied across all communication activities. A visual identity manual was produced to guide the use of the project logo, typography, colour palette, graphic elements, and design templates. To support collective communication efforts, a set of reusable materials was made available to the consortium, including templates for social media posts, presentations and posters, as well as custom email headers and video frames. In addition, a dedicated Media Centre was created on the project website, providing access to logos, promotional materials and press releases for partners and external stakeholders.

Figure 1: ProBleu visual identity guidelines; logo usage, colour palette, typography and graphic elements applied across communication materials (left), and its application to the poster template (right).

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To increase visibility, a range of branded materials was designed, including t-shirts, pens, stickers, magnetic badges, reusable water bottles and roll-up banners. These materials were used by partners during different conferences, meetings, and local events.

Figure 2: Examples of ProBleu-branded materials used by partners during conferences, meetings and local outreach events.

Beyond core branding, ProBleu placed strong emphasis on developing communication guides and toolkits to empower partners and schools to actively contribute to project communication. Funded schools received a Schools Communication Guide and Toolkit together with their contract, including communication guidelines and poster templates to support the dissemination of their local projects.

This approach enabled schools to generate their own communication content, resulting in 33% (M18) and 60% (M34) of ProBleu's social media content being produced directly by schools through a user-generated content strategy. In parallel, Partner Communication Guidelines and call-specific communication toolkits were developed, providing visuals for social media campaigns, web banners, newsletter content, press releases and multilingual videos tailored to each funding call.

Figure 3: Multilingual call factsheets produced for ProBleu funding calls and disseminated through digital channels to support outreach across Europe and associated countries.

Figure 4: Examples of user-generated content produced by funded schools and shared through ProBleu social media channels.

To address language barriers and support outreach across Europe and associated countries, summarised factsheets for each funding call were translated into more than 40 languages and disseminated through the website and targeted email campaigns.

2.2 Website

The project website (probleu.school) was developed and fed as the central digital communication hub for ProBleu. From the early stages of the project, the website provided essential information about ProBleu objectives, alignment with the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”, consortium partners and ongoing activities.

As the project progressed, the website evolved to support a growing range of communication needs linked to funding calls descriptions, documents, procedures and results, and presentation of funded school projects.

A key function of the website is to support the promotion and management of the funding calls. Dedicated sections host call documentation, templates and guidance through the *Applicants' Toolkit*, while the *Funded Projects* section was launched to showcase the projects selected for funding. This section was progressively expanded and currently includes one dedicated post per funded school project, regularly updated with descriptions, photographs and videos provided by the schools. Content creation for this section was coordinated between Earthwatch, drafting individual project stories and CSIC, overseeing content consistency and publication.

Figure 5: Examples of individual funded school project posts published on the ProBleu website and regularly updated with content provided by schools.

Once the four ProBleu funding calls were completed, the website was further adapted to reflect the overall impact of the funding programme, shifting the focus from call promotion to results and outcomes. The main funding calls landing page was updated to provide an overview of the cumulative impact of the calls, highlighting the number of funded projects, participating schools and countries, as well as the thematic diversity of the initiatives supported. This transition marked a shift from an application-oriented communication approach to a results-oriented narrative, reinforcing the role of the website as a space not only for information and access, but also for showcasing the collective contribution of ProBleu schools to ocean and freshwater literacy.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the funding calls overview page, illustrating the shift from an application-oriented to a results-oriented website narrative.

In parallel, news posts were published on a regular basis, covering project updates, success stories from funded schools, related initiatives and upcoming events. An editorial calendar supported content planning, and partners contributed articles to the blog to highlight their expertise and the multidisciplinary nature of the consortium. All website content is systematically promoted through ProBleu social media channels to amplify reach and engagement.

Figure 7: ProBleu blog posts highlight project updates, success stories and partner contributions.

As new project outputs became available, the website expanded its role as a repository of communication and educational resources. The launch and progressive growth of the Resource Catalogue strengthened the website's function as a reference point for ocean and freshwater literacy materials, while additional pages supported frequently asked questions, events and collaborations with sister projects.

In the final phase of the project, a significant share of communication actions increasingly focused on promoting the teaching aids and resources available through the online *Resource Catalogue*, positioning it as a key legacy output for teachers, schools and education networks beyond the ProBleu funding calls.

2.3 Social media activity

Social media channels were used as a supporting communication tool to facilitate mutual amplification between the project and participating schools. Over the course of the project, communication efforts progressively focused on schools as the primary target audience, prioritising content that could be easily reused, shared and adapted by educational communities.

Social media content was published in local languages whenever opportunities arose, particularly in connection with funding calls, language ambassadors' activities and school-led communication. This multilingual approach supported outreach beyond English-speaking audiences and facilitated engagement at local and national levels.

Throughout the project lifecycle, the use of social media platforms evolved in response to audience behaviour and context. While multiple platforms were initially activated, X was progressively phased out, and communication efforts increasingly concentrated on Instagram as the primary channel, given its strong visual focus and suitability for school-related content. LinkedIn was maintained as a secondary channel, mainly to reach education professionals, networks and institutional stakeholders.

Also, direct messages via Facebook and Instagram became a tool for guidance for teachers interested in participating in ProBleu, sister projects and the Network of European Blue Schools.

In addition, YouTube emerged as an increasingly relevant, unplanned communication channel. The platform is used to host and disseminate longer-form audiovisual content, including videos showcasing funded school projects, science communication materials such as PML's Science Stories, and a selection of videos produced directly by schools. This channel complemented social media activity by enabling more in-depth storytelling and by providing reusable audiovisual resources that could be embedded on the website and shared across other communication channels.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the ProBleu YouTube channel hosting long-form audiovisual content, including school project videos and science communication materials.

During the final year of the project, social media content increasingly highlighted the *Teaching Aids* hosted in the *Resource Catalogue*, encouraging reuse by schools and alignment with classroom needs.

2.4 Newsletters and direct outreach

Email communication was used as another channel to provide targeted information to schools and other stakeholders throughout the project. ProBleu implemented regular newsletter campaigns to disseminate project updates, funding opportunities, guidance materials and relevant milestones.

These newsletters were primarily addressed to schools, education networks, and interested stakeholders, supporting both the Blue Schools Network and water literacy awareness and participation in funding calls.

Beyond general newsletters, direct outreach played an important role in supporting schools throughout the application and implementation phases. Targeted email exchanges and follow-up messages were used to respond to questions, clarify requirements and provide tailored guidance, particularly during funding calls and reporting periods.

Figure 9: Examples of ProBleu newsletters disseminated in English and local languages. Specific versions per reached country; see examples here from Malta (left) and Croatia (right).

Email campaigns were sent to specific countries where we achieved an important school community database. For example, we sent emails to +2000 schools in Malta, 5000 in Croatia and 6000 in Spain. Also, **Earthwatch** prepared local-language email campaigns to at least 10 schools in each targeted EU and associated countries.

We established a WhatsApp community for ProBleu teachers to foster communication not only with ProBleu partners but also among the educators themselves. This channel is designed to remain active with minimal effort once the project concludes, while enabling us to share updates on relevant topics quickly and efficiently

Together, newsletters and direct outreach mechanisms enabled ProBleu to maintain a continuous and responsive dialogue with schools, sister projects and stakeholders, complementing broader communication channels.

2.5 Media and press-related actions

Media and press-related actions were implemented as a complementary communication activity to support the visibility of ProBleu at key moments of the project, particularly in connection with funding calls and special dates or events.

These press materials were disseminated through the communication channels of consortium partners, such as institutional websites, newsletters and press mailing lists. In some cases, press releases were coordinated with related initiatives and sister projects **SHORE** and **BlueLightS** to reinforce consistency and outreach.

Overall, media and press-related actions supported the broader communication strategy by amplifying key messages beyond the project's own channels and reinforcing ProBleu's presence within relevant networks.

Funded schools were also encouraged and supported in promoting their blue projects in local media to amplify their own impact and spread the word about the Mission Ocean.

Figure 10: Examples of media coverage from local and national media featuring ProBleu-funded school projects.

2.6 Local-language communication actions: ambassadors

Local-language communication actions were implemented to support outreach in national and regional contexts, reduce language barriers and facilitate engagement with schools across different countries. This approach was primarily carried out through the involvement of language ambassadors, who acted as intermediaries between the project and local school communities.

Language ambassadors supported communication activities by adapting and disseminating key project messages in local languages, particularly in relation to funding calls, participation requirements and project objectives. Their role included the promotion of calls at the national

level, the clarification of project information for schools, and the support of schools during the project design, application and implementation phases. This localised approach complemented central communication channels and helped ensure that information was accessible and culturally relevant.

Figure 11: Examples of local-language videos produced with the support of ProBleu language ambassadors to promote funding calls and project participation.

In addition to dissemination, language ambassadors contributed to the production and circulation of localised communication materials, including videos, visual assets and translated content, which were shared through social media, email campaigns and local networks. In some cases, ambassadors also supported or participated in information sessions and online meetings addressed to schools in their respective countries.

2.7 EU Mission project collaborations

Since the beginning of the project, ProBleu actively engaged in coordination and communication spaces linked to the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”, including regular participation in EU Mission communication coordination meetings. In parallel, ProBleu promoted bilateral and multilateral exchanges with sister projects, such as SHORE, BlueLightS and, at a later stage, PHAROS, with the aim of aligning communication efforts and creating synergies.

Figure 12: Recognition events for newly accredited Blue Schools within a Pharos - ProBleu collaboration framework in Gran Canaria (Spain).

ProBleu also participated actively in key international and European events related to the EU Mission and the Ocean Decade, including the UN Ocean Decade Conference 2024 (2024 Barcelona), Ocean Literacy World Conference (2024 Venice), the EU Ocean Days, the European Maritime Day(s), and the EMSEA Annual Conference. These spaces enabled coordination between initiatives, exchange of practices and the development of joint dissemination actions.

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Figure 13: ProBleu, SHORE and BlueLightS teams and coordinators participating in joint dissemination events, including EMSEA 2024 (top left) and the European Ocean Days 2024 (top right), and ProBleu, SHORE and BlueLightS team members at European Ocean Days and Mission Ocean Waters Forum 2026 (down).

Collaboration with sister projects translated into concrete communication synergies, including cross-promotion through guest posts on project websites and newsletters, the

dissemination of related EU project opportunities through ProBleu communication channels, and participation as invited speakers in joint webinars and events. These actions contributed to reinforcing the visibility of the Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS) and the shared objectives of the EU Mission.

In addition, ProBleu, SHORE and BlueLightS benefited from the services of the [Horizon Results Booster](#), which supported the projects in identifying the dissemination potential of their results. As a concrete outcome, the projects are currently working on joint publications, including a co-authored article submitted to the Inspire section of [Science in School](#), a free magazine for STEM teachers widely disseminated across Europe.

In parallel, ProBleu used the [Scientix](#) network to support dissemination and outreach activities within the education community. ProBleu resources and objectives were integrated into several Scientix-led initiatives, including the Science Projects Workshop “Bridging the Digital Divide in Education” (June 2025), organised by Scientix® and Xiaomi, which gathered 33 teachers and educators from 9 countries, and the Science Projects Workshop “Carbon Act” (July 2025), organised by Scientix® and Carbon Act with the support of Trane Technologies, bringing together 39 teachers, educators and project partners from 13 countries. Both workshops focused on contextualising ProBleu resources within EU competence frameworks and the Sustainable Development Goals, using integrated STEM approaches to design learning activities.

Scientix Learning Tides Award

The **Scientix Learning Tides Award**, supported by [ProBleu](#), will celebrate outstanding activities tackling the topic of ocean literacy. Create either a Learning Scenario, Story of Implementation, Video or Other. Check out the [ProBleu Resource Catalogue](#), for more dynamic online resources designed to promote water literacy and ocean education in primary and secondary schools.

Ready to show your expertise? Check [the video for instructions](#) on how to submit your entry!

Prize: Winners (x2) will be invited to the upcoming 2025 Science Projects Workshop in Brussels.

Winners:

- **Angeliki Liapi** (from Greece), for the entry “Climate change and sustainability with #CarbonAct”.
- **Emma Abbate** (from Italy), for the entry “The rising seas watchers. Scientix Learning Tides Award submission”.

Figure 14: Communication materials from the Scientix-led Learning Tides Award campaign supporting the dissemination of ProBleu resources within the education community.

Furthermore, ProBleu established an agreement to disseminate project resources through the STEM Discovery Campaign 2026, co-organised by Scientix and NBS Academy. Within this framework, ProBleu materials will be promoted as part of a Europe-wide initiative encouraging innovation in STEM education, and included in the Scientix Awards 2026, which recognise teachers and educators implementing innovative classroom practices.

3. Conclusions

The communication approach adopted by ProBleu was strongly school-centred, combining central coordination with active partner involvement and decentralised contributions from schools.

Throughout the project, communication actions were implemented following inclusive communication principles, with particular attention to reducing language barriers, improving accessibility of digital content and supporting participation from schools across diverse geographical, linguistic and socio-educational contexts.

The progressive development of communication materials, the adaptive use of digital channels and the emphasis on mutual amplification between the project and participating schools contributed to creating a dynamic and inclusive communication ecosystem aligned with the objectives of the programme and the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”.

This report does not detail the performance or impact of communication activities; these were, however, continuously monitored through project-defined indicators, as reported in Periodic Reports to the Commission. A comprehensive evaluation of the outcomes and long-term impact of ProBleu communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be presented in the Final Project Report.